

Enhanced crop calibration for SWAT+: evaluating water, sediment and nutrient impacts across ten European catchments

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Crop yield
Crop growth
Calibration workflow
Water balance
Nutrient balance
SWAT+

ABSTRACT

This study proposes a new workflow for crop growth evaluation and yield calibration in the Soil and Water Assessment Tool Plus (SWAT+) model and evaluates its impact on simulated hydrological and biogeochemical processes. The workflow was applied for ten small agricultural catchments in Europe. A detailed demonstration is provided for the German catchment, Schwarzer Schöps. The workflow proved effective across all catchments, improving yield calibration from an initial R^2 of 0.5–0.84. The results show that evapotranspiration and soil moisture were only moderately affected by crop calibration in three catchments (Belgium, Czech Republic and Norway) and negligibly changed in the remaining ones. Sediment and nutrient balance were affected more strongly: sediment, nitrogen and phosphorus loss change reached 82 % (Norway), 16 % and 20 % (Czech Republic), respectively. The proposed workflow is a valuable tool for improving the accuracy of SWAT + simulations and can be used to support decision-making in environmental management.

1. Introduction

Plant growth and hydrological processes are inextricably linked and influence each other at different scales (Asbjornsen et al., 2011). Local soil water content affects nutrient availability and plant growth, which in turn affects the rate of plant water uptake. At the landscape scale, vegetation patterns and plant growth dynamics have a significant impact on the overall water balance and the distribution of runoff components such as surface runoff or groundwater recharge. These

interactions shape ecosystem productivity and resilience, especially under changing climate conditions (Hu et al., 2024). Process-based models provide powerful tools for simulating and understanding these complex interactions and predicting how different field management practices and environmental changes might affect plant growth and water systems. Understanding how these systems respond to climate change is crucial for ensuring long-term food security and water availability (Turrall et al., 2011).

The Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT, and the new version

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SWAT+) is one of the most widely used environmental models worldwide (Gassman et al., 2014; Tan et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2019). It is highly versatile and can be used for a wide range of environmental studies. However, hydrological applications dominate the published literature (Janjić and Tadić, 2023; Zhao et al., 2024), despite the existence of a plant growth component. The plant module sets SWAT apart from many other hydrological models, yet it is unfortunately not common practice to evaluate simulated plant growth when applying the model in a hydrological context. This step is either neglected by model users or not reported in publications. However, recent studies have demonstrated that improving crop yield and biomass predictions in SWAT(+) can lead to more accurate overall simulations of hydrology and pollutant export across diverse climatic and vegetation conditions (Čerkasova et al., 2023). The process of plant growth directly affects the water and nutrient cycles, since evapotranspiration (ET) and plant uptake are key components of the respective balances of these resources. Sediment yield estimations are also influenced, as crop growth affects soil cover and the availability of plant residues, and thus susceptibility to soil erosion. Additionally, the complexity of parameterising management in the model setup carries the risk of introducing errors that can easily be overlooked.

From a hydrological perspective, it is expected that a lack of crop yield calibration leads to under- or overestimation of ET, which is compensated during the 'hard' calibration of hydrology by over-adjusting the parameter values to achieve a good fit of simulated and observed discharge time series. Thus, several studies have provided good examples for crop growth evaluation and yield calibration using SWAT and SWAT + models. Musyoka et al. (2021) developed a multi-step calibration approach for SWAT that included a manual calibration of crop yields and spatial validation of the obtained parameters. Čerkasova et al. (2023) utilized SWAT + to simulate corn and soybean yields across the contiguous United States and achieved a good agreement between simulated and reported yields by using the semi-automated soft-calibration module of SWAT+. Plunge et al. (2024a) recently provided a new tool to facilitate the verification of SWAT + model setups, including crop management and plant growth. This is a critical prerequisite for calibrating crop yields, as the complexity and possibilities of SWAT(+) can easily lead to confusion when parameterising crop management. The importance of calibrating plant growth parameters to reduce hydrological modelling errors has also been emphasised in studies by Nair et al. (2011) and Sinnathamby et al. (2017), as well as in studies introducing new crop varieties to SWAT (e.g. Trybula et al., 2015). It has been demonstrated that incorporating crop yield calibration improved prediction efficiencies, particularly with regard to nutrient balances, and to a lesser extent with respect to water balance components. However, there is currently no consensus on the most effective approach to crop yield calibration in SWAT(+), partly due to a lack of knowledge about the impact of yield calibration on different simulated processes across different soil-climatic regions. Moreover, to our knowledge, apart from the in-built SWAT + crop softcal module which is poorly documented, there are no openly available tools or scripted workflows specifically designed to help with crop yield calibration in SWAT+, which many model users could benefit from.

In light of this, the primary objective of this study is to evaluate the impact of crop yield calibration on simulated hydrological and biogeochemical processes within the SWAT + model. Focusing on ten small agricultural catchments in Europe, the study proposes a new workflow for crop growth evaluation and yield calibration. As a practical illustration of the workflow, we first demonstrate its application for a German catchment, Schwarzer Schöps. Next, we present the synthesis of crop yield calibration across all studied catchments and analyse the effect of calibration on simulated actual evapotranspiration, soil moisture, sediment, nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) balance for cropland areas within each catchment. While 44 unique crops were used in the ten model setups of this study, a representative subset of eight crops was

selected for the core analysis, covering a wide range of crop classes: cereals, oilseeds, tubers, and fodder crops.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area

This study deals with ten small agricultural catchments located predominantly in central and northern Europe, within the Continental, Pannonian and Boreal biogeographical regions (Fig. 1). These catchments are a subset of case studies investigated within the EU Horizon 2020 project OPTAIN ("OPTimal strategies to rETAIN and re-use water and nutrients in small agricultural catchments across different soil-climatic regions in Europe"¹). They represent a broad range of soil-climatic zones and agricultural systems. While the catchment sizes are relatively homogenous, ranging between 50 and 175 km², the proportion of cropland varies widely, from 13 to 89 % (Table 1). The reader is referred to Magnier et al. (2024) for more details about the project goals and case studies. Throughout the paper, we will refer to catchments by their country codes, as shown in Table 1.

2.2. SWAT + description

The Soil and Water Assessment Tool is a widely used open-source modeling tool that can simulate a comprehensive range of hydrological processes, sediment and nutrient cycles, and vegetation growth, including crop production. Over the 45 years of development, the SWAT source code has undergone significant modifications, as documented by Gassman and Wang (2015) through SWAT version 2012. The code has since evolved into the SWAT+, a restructured version described by Bieger et al. (2017). Changes in SWAT + include varying levels of complexity for simulating land phase and water routing processes, the ability to maintain field management schedules and operations as database-like structures, flexibility in defining variables that affect the timing of management operations, and the simulation of plant communities.

The tool is programmed using the object-oriented programming language Fortran90. The most up-to-date SWAT + code, along with its revision history, can be found at the SWAT + source code GitHub repository (Arnold et al., 2024). We used the SWAT + revision 2024.61.0.1 (dated September 17th, 2024). In this section, we will refer to an "object" as a plain structure containing attributes and methods in the SWAT + code, a term common in object-oriented programming.

2.2.1. Plant growth module

The original SWAT plant growth module is a simplified version of the corresponding module in the Environmental Policy Integrated Climate (EPIC) model (Williams et al., 1989). Since then, several plant growth improvements and additions have been incorporated into SWAT+. Now SWAT + partitions plant parts (objects) into leaves, stems, roots, and seeds, which makes the code more transparent and easier to maintain, while giving physical meaning to harvest operations for the user (Supplementary Material Fig. S1). Users can choose to harvest grain, root, or biomass and specify a Harvest Index (HI) in the harvest management operations. The root harvest operation specifies the ratio of root yield to total root biomass, while the biomass harvest specifies the ratio of biomass yield to total above-ground biomass. For the grain harvest operation, users input an optimum and minimum harvest index (the ratio of grain harvested to total above-ground biomass). The actual HI is computed based on actual and potential water uptake, as described in Neitsch et al. (2011), and is bounded by the optimum and minimum HI.

An additional enhancement to the SWAT + code is the

¹ <https://www.optain.eu/>.

Fig. 1. Location of study catchments in Europe. Labels refer to country-specific catchment codes used throughout the paper (see Table 1).

Table 1

Summary of the studied catchments, grouped by biogeographical region (EEA - European Environment Agency, 2003) and sorted from north to south.

Catchment code	Name	Country	Biogeographical region	Catchment area [km ²]	Share of cropland [%]
NO	Kråkstad	Norway	Boreal	50	43.5
LT	Dotnuvele	Lithuania	Boreal	175	72.9
PL	Upper Zgłowiączka	Poland	Continental	150	88.6
DE	Schwarzer Schöps	Germany	Continental	137	47.5
BE	La Wimbe	Belgium	Continental	116	13.1
CZ	Cechticky	Czech Republic	Continental	71	51.5
CH	Petite Glâne	Switzerland	Continental	100	63.0
HU1	Felső-Válicka	Hungary	Pannonian	124	24.4
HU2	Tetves	Hungary	Pannonian	79	26.1
IT	Cherio	Italy	Continental	144	27.6

implementation of an organic object that includes total carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus. This object is utilized for various plant parts, including roots, leaves, stalks, seeds, above-ground biomass, and total biomass. By using an organic object to store each component and partitioning them daily, the model can simulate the transfer of nutrients

between different plant parts (e.g., from above ground to roots), making the plant growth simulation more realistic. SWAT + uses a plant-specific radiation use efficiency, intercepted photosynthetically active radiation, and Leaf Area Index (LAI) to calculate potential daily biomass increase. Similar to the previous SWAT version (Neitsch et al., 2011), SWAT +

accounts for limitations on plant growth (called “stresses”) caused by sub-optimal temperatures (both below the minimum and above the optimum for plant growth), water scarcity, and insufficient nitrogen or phosphorus. Additionally, SWAT + includes an algorithm from the Agricultural Policy/Environmental eXtender (APEX) model (Gassman et al., 2014; Williams et al., 1989) that calculates aeration stress from excess water based on soil water content and a plant-specific aeration factor. With the introduction of the salinity module (in active development for SWAT+), it becomes possible to simulate plant stress caused by high salt concentrations in the environment (Bailey et al., 2019).

Crop Heat Unit (HU) systems measure the thermal environment of plants and are often used in phenology models to link plant growth and development to local climate conditions. The HU are calculated for each day and accumulated from planting to the harvest date. For wintering crops, the HU are reset after 1 January (for the northern hemisphere) or 1 July (for the southern hemisphere), and the base temperature is set at zero degrees Celsius (base zero heat units). The crop is considered to be dormant when temperatures are below zero degrees. After the reset, the HU accumulation for each crop is triggered at 0.15 base zero heat units. Previously, SWAT users relied on an external Potential Heat Unit (PHU) program that calculated the heat units required for plant maturity based on historical temperature data, a plant’s minimum growth temperature and average days to maturity. In contrast, SWAT + now offers a more adaptable approach to simulating plant growth. A key improvement is incorporating a heat unit estimate directly within the model’s internal calculation while the user inputs the “days to maturity” parameter for each plant or crop. The input of days to maturity allows the model to simulate different crop varieties based on the length of their growing season (e.g., crop varieties for 120, 100, 90 days to maturity, etc.). The days to maturity approach allows SWAT + to estimate heat units accurately for both the northern and southern hemispheres, taking into account seasonal variations.

Days to maturity for each crop in the default SWAT + database (plants.plt input file) were assigned to each crop by the SWAT + development team. The days to maturity were estimated by computing the difference between the typical planting and harvesting dates for each crop from the NRCS RUSLE2 Crop Management Templates database (RUSLE2 Program, 2022) and rounded to tens. Although being a straightforward approach, the SWAT + model user has to take into account the climatic and crop species variations that are relevant for their particular area and make adjustments as necessary. To ensure flexibility, the default plant database includes multiple pre-set “days to maturity” values for common crops. SWAT + users can also adjust the days to maturity (days_mat) parameter as needed during the calibration process.

2.2.2. Management actions in SWAT+

Management operations in SWAT + are referred to as actions. Key management actions are listed in Table 2. For a complete list of manual operation management actions, consult the SWAT + documentation.²

In the SWAT+, management scheduling is a crucial component that allows users to simulate various agricultural field management practices. Moreover, SWAT + allows for the simulation of complex crop rotations and multi-year management plans by combining various operations and adjusting their timing and intensity. This is achieved through the use of decision tables and/or manual management schedules.

The manual schedules specify the timing of various operations based on specific dates (month and day) or heat units, while decision tables automate the management actions based on logical conditions set by the user. In this study, we used manual operation scheduling based on dates. For instance, planting (plnt) and harvesting (harv) dates were tailored to reflect local agricultural practices and crop varieties. Fertilizer

applications (fert) were scheduled based on crop growth stages at various timings in combination with weather conditions, and tillage operations (till) were specified to mimic different cultivation techniques, i.e. low tillage practices. This detailed representation of management actions ensures a realistic and comprehensive simulation of agricultural processes in the SWAT + model applications and is a distinct and often underutilised capability of this tool.

2.3. Model setups

This study is unique for its meticulous focus on agricultural fields and a harmonized approach to modeling. Initial model setups were developed in a harmonized and fully scripted way, following the guidelines of the OPTAIN SWAT + modelling protocol (Schürz et al., 2022; Piniewski et al., 2024). Whenever possible, the modelling teams used the best available local input data (typically in the case of the DEM, soil and land use map, weather data). Input data processing was facilitated by the use of the SWATprepR R package (Plunge et al., 2024a). In the description below we focus on those aspects of the model setups that are most important for this study. The reader is referred to OPTAIN reports (Schürz et al., 2022; Piniewski et al., 2024) for more specific information.

All field parcels were implemented as individual hydrological response units (HRUs) in the SWAT + model setups. We combined local data, such as administrative field block information and remote sensing data, to delineate individual agricultural fields precisely. Due to the contiguous object connectivity approach applied in the model setup process (Schürz et al., 2022), all HRUs are spatially connected to their surrounding landscape (neighbouring HRUs and water objects), which provides a detailed representation of field-specific characteristics and their influence on water and nutrient dynamics in the model setup.

Crop rotations were derived through a combination of remote sensing data, local farmer knowledge, and regional administrative datasets and were extended for the simulation periods. Although such data provide information on the sequences of planted and harvested crops, the exact sequences of farm management operations, such as planting, fertilizer application, or tillage and their timings, are hardly available for all agricultural parcels of a catchment. To ensure a realistic representation of agricultural practices, typical region-specific management schedules have been developed for each crop based on expert knowledge and information from local farmers or farm advisors. The developed management schedules include typical time windows for all operations. For each field, the individual, single-year crop management schedules were assembled to form the management schedules for the crop rotations. The operation dates for these rotations were dynamically generated using the SWATfarmR (Schürz and Lima, 2024) package, enabling the model to account for weather-dependent variations in farming activities. This harmonized model setup process, documented in the modeling protocol (Schürz et al., 2022), was consistently applied across all case study sites to ensure the robustness of the results and good comparability between the case studies. The tools used are open-access, and the methods, including a complete description of the model setup methodology, are described in detail in the modeling protocol. Therefore, this approach can be repeated in any area, given data availability. The following sections of this paper focus on crop management-specific setup details.

Forty-four unique crops from the plants.plt file were used in the ten model setups of this study (Fig. 2 and Table S1 in the Supplementary Material). Crop selection for calibration in each catchment was determined by the respective modeling teams. In general, crops comprising more than 5 % of the total agricultural area were included. For the synthesis of results in section 3.2, a representative subset of eight crops was chosen to maintain a manageable scope. Seven crops with a frequency of occurrence higher than or equal to 40 % across catchments were selected in the first stage: winter wheat (‘wwhwt’, ten occurrences); winter barley (‘wbar’, six occurrences); and five crops occurring four

² https://swatplus.gitbook.io/io-docs/introduction/landuse-and-management/management.sch/op_typ.

Table 2
The most common types of management actions used in SWAT+ and their additional parameterisation options.

SWAT + management code (op_type)	Operation	Description	Additional Operation data 1 (op_data1)	Additional Operation data 2 (op_data2)	Additional Operation data 3 (op_data3)
plnt	Planting	Initialization of the growth of a specific plant type or plant community in the HRU	Type of plant from the plant initialization file, i.e. <i>wwht</i>		
harv	Harvest	Harvests the portion of the plant designated as yield and removes the yield from the HRU, but allows the plant to continue to grow (e.g. hay cuttings)	Type of plant from the plant initialization file, i.e. <i>wwht</i>	Specifies the plant part to be harvested from the available harvest operations: biomass, grain, residue, tree, tuber, peanuts, stripper, picker, etc.	
kill	Kill only	The operation kills the plant and converts the plant biomass to residue on the soil surface	Type of plant from the plant initialization file, i.e. <i>wwht</i>		
hvk1	Harvest and kill	The operation harvests the portion of the plant designated as yield, removes the yield from the HRU and converts the remaining plant biomass to residue on the soil surface	Type of plant from the plant initialization file, i.e. <i>wwht</i>	Specifies the plant part to be harvested from the available harvest operations: biomass, grain, residue, tree, tuber, peanuts, stripper, picker, etc.	
till	Tillage	Mixes the upper soil layers and redistributes the nutrients and other chemicals within those layers	Type of equipment from the tillage database file, i.e. <i>rowcult</i>		
fert	Fertilizer application	Operation adds nutrients to the soil on the specified day	Type of fertilizer from the fertilizer database file, i.e. <i>elem_n</i>	Surface application option from chemical application database file, i.e. <i>broadcast</i>	Amount applied in kg/ha (dry matter)
graz	Grazing	This operation removes plant biomass at a specified rate and simultaneously applies manure	Type of grazing from the grazing database file	Amount of days that the operation occurred	
skip	Skipping	This operation skips to the end of the year			

Fig. 2. Crop structure in the study catchments presented as treemap charts.

times: alfalfa ('alfa'); spring barley ('barl'); winter rapeseed ('canp'³); grain corn ('corn') and silage corn ('csil'). In addition, sugar beet ('sgbt') was selected as the only tuber crop to enrich the crop subset, even though it occurred only in three catchments. Thus, the eight crops used in the analysis include a wide range of crop classes: cereals, oilseed, tuber, and fodder crops.

2.4. Workflow

The overall workflow is visualised in Fig. 3. It provides an overview of the semi-automated calibration approach developed for this study and the preparatory steps required. It has been applied to a wide range of crops and soil-climatic conditions across Europe. The effects of the crop calibration on the simulated actual evapotranspiration, soil moisture, sediment and nutrient balances were then analysed.

2.4.1. Preparatory steps - reference data and crop growth verification

The calibration workflow begins with an initial (uncalibrated) SWAT + model setup, including defined management schedules and a list of crops to be included in the calibration and subsequent analyses. In this context, 'uncalibrated' refers to a model that has not undergone any kind of calibration. Additional data requirements are modest: the approach relies on multi-annual averages and ranges of crop yields. In this study, yield data were acquired from local sources or regional statistics (Supplementary Material Table S3). Since SWAT + simulates crop yield as dry matter, the reference data (often reported as fresh matter) must be converted using crop-specific conversion factors, ideally obtained from national data. Dry matter conversion factors of agricultural products are often provided as an appendix to national fertiliser regulations, e.g. Bundesministerium für Ernährung und Landwirtschaft (2017), but international standards are also available (Ronzon et al., 2015; EUROSTAT, 2020). In cases where specific crops are unavailable in the plant parameter database (e.g., new crop varieties), it is advisable to first adopt the parameter set of a similar plant species. It is then recommended to search the relevant literature for specific parameters (e.g. Sinnathamby et al., 2017; Trybula et al., 2015; Koocheki et al., 2016; Özdemir et al., 2024) and to calibrate the parameters using local crop yield time series.

All case studies included in this analysis conducted a verification of their model setups prior to crop calibration using the R package SWATdoctR (Plunge et al., 2024b). The proposed crop growth verification process involves three steps: (1) verifying that the agricultural management operations are performed correctly during the model run; (2) examining the crop growth simulation without the crop growth stressors activated; (3) examining the crop growth with the crop growth stresses activated.

Steps 1 and 2 are best carried out on a crop-by-crop basis, checking the field management practices, timing, rates, subsequent LAI development and optimum crop yield achieved. Fig. S3 in the Supplementary Material shows an example from the German catchment where the analyses of the daily time series of HRU-related plant variables verified the plausibility of crop phenology (LAI and biomass development) and the planting and harvesting dates for all considered crop types. If errors in the management parameterisation can be ruled out, the crop parameterisation (plants.plt) and dry matter conversion factors should be checked.

The following analysis of stresses (Figs. S4–S5) can assist in identifying additional issues in the management input, such as deficiencies in fertiliser inputs or adjustments to the timing of specific operations. Potential issues with climate input, initialization of soil nutrients, and

³ Since winter rapeseed is missing in the SWAT + plants.plt file, 'canp' parameters were used as the starting point and adjusted using expert knowledge, namely Jim Kiniry (USDA, ARS) and Manyowa (Norman) Meki (Texas A&M Agrilife Research).

atmospheric deposition have also been considered. In the event of outliers emerging in the simulated crop yields, the spatial distribution of these outliers was checked, as well as the spatial distribution of the stress factors and the parameterisation of the corresponding HRUs.

2.4.2. Crop calibration

A two-step calibration of crop growth and yield was performed in this study (Fig. 3). This process aimed to align SWAT + simulations with target values of potential heat units (PHU) and observed yields by adjusting relevant crop parameters. This semi-automated calibration procedure uses approaches first developed by Piniewski et al. (2024) and subsequently published as the R package SWATtunR (Plunge et al., 2025). The only data this approach relies on are the mean and ranges of the observed yields of selected crops for the simulation period. Due to the use of average observed values rather than time series, it can be referred to as a 'soft' approach for crop calibration (Arnold et al., 2015). However, it involves parameter sampling and multiple model runs, which is less typical for soft calibration approaches.

The first step of crop calibration was to match crop-specific target PHU values by adjusting the 'days_mat' (days to maturity) parameter. A semi-automated scripted workflow, available on the R package SWATtunR Github page (Plunge et al., 2025), was developed to achieve this. The scripted workflow applies changes to the initial 'days_mat' values and runs the SWAT + simulations, extracting the resulting PHU fractions, biomass and yields. The results are presented as a box plot analysis (thus demonstrating catchment-average values and variability across HRUs) and require a manual selection of the final parameter value. The goal was to achieve a PHU fraction between 1.0 and 1.2 for most cereal crops and 0.5 to 0.9 for silage crops, with yields falling within a plausible range. These PHU ranges are supported by the theoretical basis of the SWAT model, where plant growth is simulated until the crop reaches maturity at PHU = 1.0 (Neitsch et al., 2009, ch. 5.1.1.1). In practice, many crops are harvested after maturity — often following a short drying period in the field — resulting in PHU values slightly greater than 1.0. Further evidence is provided in the SWAT I/O documentation (Arnold et al., 2012; Appendix A), which summarizes PHU accumulation across development stages for multiple crops. Extrapolating from these references, together with personal communications with Dr. J. R. Kiniry, the calibration target ranges for PHU were established as representative for cereal and silage crops in the SWAT + plant database. Note that it is difficult to define a reasonable PHU target fraction for crops harvested multiple times a year, such as farmland grass.

The second step involved the actual crop yield calibration. Four plant parameters: 'bm_e' (biomass-energy ratio), 'harv_idx' (harvest index for optimal growth conditions), 'tmp_base' (minimum temperature for plant growth), and 'lai_pot' (maximum potential leaf area index) were identified as most influential through initial testing. We applied the Latin Hypercube Sampling, which generates 50–100 parameter sets, applying a relative change method for 'bm_e' (+10 %, -30 %), 'harv_idx' (± 30 %), and 'lai_pot' (± 30 %), and an absolute change of ± 1.5 for 'tmp_base'. "Doty plot graphs" visualize the crop yield responses to individual parameter changes, guiding further adjustments to parameter ranges, if needed. An average error of less than 10 % was targeted. Finally, the calibrated parameters were incorporated into the plants.plt file.

2.4.3. Effect of crop calibration on water, sediment and nutrients

The last step of the analysis performed in this study concerned investigating the effect of crop calibration on simulated hydrological and biogeochemical processes (Fig. 3). To this end, for each catchment, two SWAT + simulations were performed: one with the initial (uncalibrated) model (default plants.plt file) and one with the calibrated model (modified plants.plt). The goal was to investigate the effect of calibration on hydrology (actual evapotranspiration and its components, as well as soil moisture), sediment yield and nutrient balance (N and P inputs, losses, and plant uptake). We extracted respective model outputs

Fig. 3. Overview of the workflow of the study, including a multi-step crop calibration approach for SWAT + models. The semi-automated crop calibration (middle grey box) represents the core of the calibration workflow but requires several preparatory steps (top grey box). The approach was applied to 10 case studies to analyse the effects of crop calibration on hydrological and biogeochemical processes (bottom grey box).

(Table 3) from cropland HRUs to make the results comparable between catchments. HRU-level multi-annual average values were spatially averaged over cropland HRUs and plotted for each catchment and model setup (initial vs. calibrated). Note that no calibration of hydrology, sediment and nutrients was made, since the goal was to capture the pure effect of crop calibration.

3. Results

3.1. Crop yield calibration

The proposed two-step calibration approach was applied to eight crops in the DE catchment, resulting in a reasonable agreement between simulated and observed PHU fractions and yields for each crop (Fig. 4).

As a first step, we calibrated the PHU fractions at harvest by adjusting the '*days_mat*' values. Significant changes were only required for 'sgbt' (+80 days) and 'wwht' (-50 days), while the initial PHU fractions at harvest (green boxes in Fig. 5) for the rest of the crops were already within reasonable ranges and required no or only minor changes (+/-10 days).

In the second step, we fine-tuned the parameters that directly influence crop yields. The simulations with 100 Latin-Hypercube-sampled variations in four plant parameters ('*lai_pot*', '*harv_idx*', '*tmp_base*', and '*bm_e*'; Fig. 6) allowed us to identify the most yield-sensitive parameters for each crop and determine the direction and magnitude of adjustments needed to match observed yields. The specific adjustments (e.g., reducing '*harv_idx*' for barley (barl) by 20 %, increasing '*lai_pot*' for sugar beet (sgbt) by 30 %, and '*bm_e*' by 10 %) correspond to the relative parameter changes at which simulated yields aligned with the observed mean yield (vertical green lines in Fig. 6). These percentages differ

among crops because each crop responds differently to parameter variation, as shown by the slopes and ranges in the sensitivity plots.

As a result, the simulated yields of each crop in the DE catchment agree well with the observed yields while ensuring that they reach a plausible state of maturity (PHU fraction) at the time of harvest (Fig. 4). However, it is noticeable that there are downward outliers (black dots below boxplots) in the simulated biomass and, hence, crop yields. This is mainly due to aeration stress for HRUs located in thalwegs or other topographical depressions, which can, therefore, receive large amounts of water from connected upper parts of the catchment and tend to be water-saturated for extended periods.

3.2. Synthesis of crop calibration results across catchments

The proposed calibration of crop yields using the method presented in this study was successful, as shown by the fact that the average annual crop yields matched the observation data for most crops after the calibration in ten study catchments (Fig. 7). In 60 % of the cases, simulated yields were increased during calibration. The R^2 between simulated and observed yield calculated across all 48 crop-catchment combinations from Fig. 7 increased from 0.5 to 0.84 after calibration. In several cases, e.g. for barley ('barl') in the BE catchment, silage corn ('csil') in the CH catchment or winter wheat ('wwht') in the NO catchment, the improvement achieved during calibration was very large. The median absolute values of percent bias in the average simulated yield show an improvement for seven out of eight crops (Table 4) and nine out of ten catchments (Table 5). The most problematic crop was the winter rapeseed ('canp'), for which the results were unsatisfactory in both Hungarian catchments (HU1 and HU2). Winter rapeseed was a new crop added to the default *plants.plt* database in this study hence, its

Table 3
Indicators used to evaluate crop calibration effects on water, sediment and nutrients.

Group	Indicator	SWAT + output
Hydrology	Plant ET [mm]	'eplant'
	Soil ET [mm]	'esoil'
	Canopy ET [mm]	'ecanopy'
	Volumetric topsoil water content [-]	'sw_300' ^a
Sediment	Sediment yield [t/ha]	'sedyld'
Nutrients	Nitrogen inputs [kg/ha] ^b	'ftrtn'+ 'fixn'+ 'no3atmo'+ 'nh4atmo'
	Denitrification [kg/ha]	'denit'
	Nitrogen losses [kg/ha] ^c	'sedorgn'+ 'surqno3'+ 'lat3no3'+ 'tileno3'+ 'percn'
	Nitrogen uptake [kg/ha]	'uptake'
	Phosphorus inputs [kg/ha]	'fertp'
	Phosphorus losses [kg/ha] ^d	'sedorgp'+ 'surqsolp'+ 'lchlabp'+ 'tilelabp'
	Phosphorus uptake [kg/ha]	'puptake'

^a Original values were standardized by the topsoil depth equal to 300 mm 'sw_300' represents average soil moisture values for the time step in SWAT+.

^b Sum of N in fertilizers, N fixation, NO₃-N and NH₄-N in atmospheric deposition.

^c Sum of organic N in surface runoff, NO₃-N in surface runoff, NO₃-N in lateral flow, NO₃-N in tile flow and percolation nitrogen.

^d Sum of organic P in surface runoff, soluble P in surface runoff, soluble P leaching past the bottom of the soil layer and labile P in tile flow.

parameterisation is quite uncertain.

The 'days_mat' parameter for winter wheat, the only crop present in all model setups, was consistently reduced in all catchments since the default value of 160 days from the 'plants.plt' file was too high for a winter cereal under European conditions (Fig. 8). The reduction rate of 'days_mat' varied between -40 and -105 days. Of the four other parameters adjusted in the 'wwht' yield calibration, 'harv_idx' was the only one that changed in all catchments. It was increased in seven out of nine cases. Changes in 'lai_pot', 't_base' and 'bm_e' were less frequent. Note that the IT catchment model setup included silage wheat, which resulted in significantly higher changes for 'days_mat' and 'lai_pot'.

Reductions of 'days_mat' during PHU calibration were also frequent for other cereals: 'wbar' and 'barl' (Fig. 8). In contrast, increases of 'days_mat' occurred more frequently for 'corn' and 'sgbt'. For other crops, changes were either lower or less consistent. Alterations of other parameters during crop yield calibration varied across catchments and parameters. 'Tmp_base' was altered the least frequently. Increases in 'lai_pot' were considerably more frequent than decreases. For 'harv_idx' and 'bm_e', the directions of changes were less consistent.

3.3. Effect of crop calibration on water, sediment, and nutrients

Before using the calibrated models to investigate the effect of crop calibration on water, sediment and nutrients, we attempted to verify the indicator values in Table 3 against observational data collated by local modelling teams (see Electronic Supplementary Material, Table S4). A direct comparison is often hampered by mismatched time periods or spatial scales (the reported simulated values represent cropland averages within study catchments, whereas the observations are typically catchment averages or field-scale values). An additional verification source was ET estimates from the field-scale soil hydrological model SWAP, which are available for several catchments (Farkas et al., 2025). Considering that the simulated values originate from an uncalibrated model, the level of agreement is satisfactory.

Fig. 4. Simulated PHU fraction at harvest/kill operation and yield (dry matter) after crop calibration for the DE catchment. Dashed lines in the first row denote the optimal range of PHU for most crops (except fodder crops). Red lines in the second row denote minimum, mean and maximum observed yields of respective crops. Boxes, whiskers and outliers refer to a subset of simulated, crop-specific annual values at HRU level.

Fig. 5. Simulated Potential Heat Unit (PHU) fraction at harvest and kill operation and simulated dry matter yield and biomass values in response to changes in the days to maturity ('days_mat') for selected crops in the DE catchment. Dashed lines in the first row denote the optimal range of PHU for most crops (except fodder crops). Red lines in the second row denote minimum, mean and maximum observed yields of respective crops. Boxes, whiskers and outliers refer to a subset of simulated, crop-specific annual values at HRU level. The different colours of the boxes were used for better readability.

The crop calibration process conducted in this study led to low or moderate changes in simulated actual ET (Fig. 9A). The most remarkable decreases occurred for the BE (−7.9 %), NO (−4.7 %), and CZ catchments (−3.8 %) while in the remaining seven catchments changes did not exceed ± 2 %. ET components were affected more strongly than the ET itself. For most catchments, canopy and plant ET components decreased, while soil ET increased after crop calibration. The highest alterations of ET composition were found for BE and NO catchments. The average annual root zone soil moisture increased in most catchments (Fig. 9B), notably in CZ catchment (by 10.6 %) and BE, HU2 and NO catchments (by 4.6–5.6 %). Increases in soil moisture were correlated with decreases in soil ET.

Sediment and nutrient indicators were affected more strongly than the water balance indicators (Fig. 10). Crop calibration led to increases in average annual sediment yield in eight out of ten catchments (Fig. 10A), with a remarkably high increase for the NO catchment (82 %), followed by HU1, BE and CZ (38 %, 19 % and 19 %, respectively). Simulated sediment loss was negligible in two catchments with particularly flat topography (LT and PL), so the changes resulting from crop calibration were unnoticeable.

Crop calibration also affected nitrogen inputs through changes in N

fixation (Fig. S6). This happened only for catchments with N-fixing plants, such as alfalfa or clover (Fig. 2). The highest changes in N inputs were noted for CZ and IT catchment (a decrease of 16 % and an increase of 8 %, respectively) (Fig. S6). N uptake by plants was reduced in most catchments, with the rate of increase reaching 20 % for the CZ catchment and 14 % for the NO catchment (Fig. 10B). Changes in simulated N losses were less consistent, varying from a decrease of 25 % (NO catchment) to an increase of 32 % (IT catchment). Simulated N loss by denitrification was relatively low compared to N uptake and N lost via hydrological pathways, so the changes were hardly noticeable.

Since P fertilization is the only P input in SWAT+, crop calibration did not affect this indicator. Variable changes in P uptake by plants were noted (Fig. 10C). Considerable decreases in P uptake (by 13–17 %) occurred for three catchments (BE, CZ, NO), while increases of similar magnitude happened for IT and LT catchments. A decreased P uptake implied higher P losses for most catchments. The greatest increases in P losses ranging from 6 % to 20 % were observed for the BE, CZ, HU1 and NO catchments.

Fig. 6. Median and min/max ranges of dry matter yields for selected crops in the DE catchment in response to Latin-Hypercube sampled changes ($n = 100$) in the parameters 'lai_pot' (maximum potential leaf area index), 'harv_idx' (harvest index for optimal growth conditions), 'tmp_base' (minimum temperature for plant growth), and 'bm_e' (biomass-energy ratio). Vertical green lines represent the manually selected parameter values (dashed = no change, solid = change in the parameter value).

4. Discussion

The new crop calibration workflow developed for SWAT+ and presented in this study proved its adaptability to different case studies across Europe. It has been successfully applied by different modelling teams independently handling their model setups. It yielded a reasonable agreement between simulated and target PHU fractions at harvest and yields for each crop. The workflow also revealed patterns in how yields and model performance vary across space and climate, as well as patterns in simulated water, sediment, and nutrient indicators.

The goodness of fit of the crop yield simulation can be considered satisfactory, with an R^2 of 0.84, which is in the range of values reported by Čerkasova et al. (2023) in a similar study implementing a different crop yield calibration procedure for a large-scale model covering the United States (R^2 of 0.7 for soybean and 0.9 for corn). Over 75 % of the PBIAS values across all 48 crop-catchment combinations were within the range of ± 25 %, similar to the study of Musyoka et al. (2021), who reported PBIAS values not exceeding 35 % for a small agricultural catchment in Austria. Other studies also reported goodness-of-fit values for yield time series data for different crops (Eini et al., 2023; Nair et al., 2011; Sinnathamby et al., 2017). Our study does not provide a model

evaluation for the temporal variability of yields. In some countries, annual yield observations are scarce or, if available, are not representative of small catchments. For this reason, we opted for a soft calibration approach in this study, which requires only average annual yield data for different crops. This should also lead to broader adoption of our approach by other researchers, which is urgently needed as more and more studies include crop yield itself as one of their research objectives (Chen et al., 2019, 2021; Kaim et al., 2021; Lautenbach et al., 2013).

Our study demonstrates that the default SWAT + plant parameters, developed in the U.S., do not necessarily fit European conditions. The strongest evidence was found for the most common crop, winter wheat, for which days to maturity were unequivocally overestimated by 40–60 days, while the harvest index values were underestimated by 15–40 %. Increased harvest index values returned by the SWAT + crop calibration procedure were also reported by Čerkasova et al. (2023) for corn and soybean and Musyoka et al. (2021) for corn, winter wheat, and rapeseed. Increasing the harvest index of wheat in this study was necessary to match observed yields which were significantly underestimated in most catchments with default parametrization. Due to the presence of equifinality of model parameters (Beven, 1993), not all patterns of changes in parameters across catchments resulting from model calibration can be

Fig. 7. Relative difference in average annual yields before and after crop yield calibration for studied catchments. Red dashed lines denote zero error values.

Table 4

Median absolute values of percent bias in average simulated yield for initial and calibrated model setups for different crops. The number in parentheses denotes the number of catchments for each crop.

Crop	Initial	Calibrated
wwht (10)	38 %	4.6 %
wbar (7)	16 %	5.6 %
barl (6)	26 %	1.6 %
corn (5)	38 %	7.8 %
canp (5)	32 %	56 %
sgbt (4)	29 %	15 %
alfa (6)	55 %	6.2 %
csil (5)	29 %	5.7 %

Table 5

Median absolute values of percent bias in average simulated yield for initial and calibrated model setups for study catchments. The number in parentheses denotes the number of crops for each catchment.

Catchment	Initial	Calibrated
NO (2)	47 %	19 %
LT (7)	48 %	27 %
PL (6)	36 %	2.9 %
DE (5)	28 %	4.6 %
BE (5)	97 %	3.0 %
CZ (4)	22 %	6.7 %
CH (6)	31 %	6.7 %
HU1 (5)	28 %	35 %
HU2 (5)	15 %	9.5 %
IT (3)	40 %	12 %

easily explained.

It is important to acknowledge that the parameters for most common crops included in the default SWAT + plant database are primarily based on US-specific studies or derived from them. This may limit the applicability of these parameters to other regions with different environmental conditions and agricultural practices. Therefore, it is recommended to carefully evaluate the suitability of these parameters for specific study areas and consider adjusting them based on local data and expert knowledge. The most striking example in this study was winter rapeseed. No such crop exists in the default SWAT + database, so the Polish canola ('canp') parameters were used as the starting point and

adjusted using expert knowledge. Nevertheless, matching both target PHU values and yields for this crop appeared challenging, as the example of two Hungarian catchments showed.

Overall, the ranges of simulated ET and soil moisture derived from the initial (uncalibrated) model setups are reasonable for all SWAT + models, and comparable to the results of field-scale SWAP modelling performed at several of the case study sites (Farkas et al., 2025). Our study showed low sensitivity of these hydrological processes to crop yield calibration, which agrees with existing literature (Nair et al., 2011; Musyoka et al., 2021). Scholz et al. (2024) used a principal component analysis of a large set of soil moisture time series from seven distinct crops in Germany to demonstrate that more than 76 % of the variance was explained by meteorological drivers and the effects of soil texture. Only 19 % of the variance was attributed to the crops and their management, with crop types and their general seasonal behaviour being the most relevant factor (17 %). Lee et al. (2022) demonstrated that incorporating crop yield into model calibration substantially reduced model uncertainty, particularly with regard to the extent of parameter equifinality. However, the absolute effect on modeled ET was shown to be rather small, except for the July peaks. This highlights that the low average sensitivity of crop yield calibration to ET and soil moisture is also partly due to the short period of the year during which yield calibration has a significant impact. For individual events the magnitude of the difference can be much higher. However, this was beyond the scope of this study, which analysed long-term averages across several case studies. In some study catchments, (e.g. in Italy), the effects on hydrological processes were further masked by irrigation. However, our study adds to the existing knowledge by showing the variability in hydrological response to crop calibration across Europe. In most cases, crop calibration led to slightly lower ET over cropland areas, mainly due to lower plant water uptake.

The sensitivity of sediment and nutrient transport to crop calibration was significantly higher than that of water balance indicators. More accurate yield simulations mean more reliable estimates of ground cover, root biomass and crop residues, all of which are central for preventing soil erosion (Sinnathamby et al., 2017; Witing and Volk, 2013). For example, in the NO catchment, sediment loss increased by 82 % after calibration, which may result from a significantly underestimated yield of the most dominant crop, winter wheat (covering 69 % of the arable land), by the default model. Higher yield was achieved by decreasing the number of days to maturity and by increasing the harvest index.

Fig. 8. Changes in parameter values after PHU and crop calibration in the study catchments. The black line denotes the original (initial) value from the plants.plt file. Circles represent calibrated values.

Decreasing ‘days_mat’ could lead to earlier harvest and reduced length of the crop period, leaving the soil surface relatively bare for a longer period than assumed in the default model setup. Increased harvest index has led to decreased availability of crop residues, also resulting in increased exposure to soil erosion.

Improving the simulation of crop yields has been shown to refine model predictions for nutrient loads, as nutrient uptake, fertilisation response, and residue management are directly tied to crop productivity (Bauwe et al., 2019; Nair et al., 2011). In most study catchments, plant nitrogen and phosphorus uptake was significantly affected by crop yield calibration. This will strengthen the upcoming nutrient calibration in general and help validate field management practices, such as fertiliser application rates. Overall, models that overlook crop calibration may suffer from considerable biases in simulated soil erosion and N/P losses. Although these biases may be compensated during the “hard” calibration of sediment and nutrients, this usually means over-adjusting certain parameters.

SWAT+ is a complex modeling tool with numerous parameters and modeled processes. Calibrating the model can be time-consuming and requires significant expertise. The proposed workflow aims to simplify the calibration process for crop growth and yield, but it still involves multiple steps and requires careful consideration of various factors. Prior to crop calibration, crop growth should be verified, e.g. using the R package SWATdoctr (Plunge et al., 2024b), to avoid an erroneous compensation of errors in crop growth simulation and agricultural management operations. Further efforts to develop user-friendly tools and guidelines could facilitate the wider adoption of the workflow and improve the accessibility of SWAT+ for a broader range of users. Moreover, the proposed workflow relies on the availability of local data, such as administrative and cultivated field information and crop yield statistics. The accuracy and completeness of these data can influence the

effectiveness of the calibration process and the reliability of the simulation results. In some regions, access to high-quality data may be limited, which could pose challenges for implementing the workflow.

The study concentrates on cultivated crops, but other plant types, especially forests, can occupy large areas and play a crucial role in hydrological and biogeochemical cycles. Future studies should consider incorporating a wider range of plant types to better understand the interactions between vegetation, water, and nutrient dynamics in different ecosystems, regions, and climates.

This study primarily focuses on rain-fed agricultural systems, with only one exception being the Italian catchment, which has irrigation. The findings and recommendations may not directly apply to irrigated systems, where water management practices can significantly influence crop growth and yield. The problem outlined in this study should be addressed differently in irrigated catchments, e.g., the analysis of actual, applied irrigation rates should be done as a part of model verification. Further research is needed to explore the impact of crop calibration on irrigated systems and develop specific guidelines for these conditions.

5. Conclusion

We developed a new crop calibration workflow for the SWAT+ ecohydrological model and validated its effectiveness across multiple European case studies representing different bio-geographical regions. Independent modeling teams successfully applied the workflow, achieving strong agreement between simulated and observed crop yields. The study also revealed the subtle influence of proper crop parameterisation on the resulting water balance components, nutrients, and sediments. We also identify key challenges and adjustments needed when applying SWAT+ outside the US. The future developments should expand or build upon the workflow to apply and adapt it to irrigated

Fig. 9. Comparison of average annual evapotranspiration (A) and root zone soil moisture (B) for the agricultural HRUs before and after crop yield calibration for study catchments.

Fig. 10. Comparison of annual average sediment (A), nitrogen (B) and phosphorus (C) balance for the agricultural HRUs before and after crop yield calibration for study catchments.

crops and other plant types. We call upon the SWAT + modelling community to not overlook crop growth evaluation and calibration in their model applications focusing on water quantity and quality and encourage them to adapt the workflow in their modeling endeavours.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mikołaj Piniewski: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Natalja Čerkasova:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Svajunas Plunge:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Michael Strauch:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology. **Christoph Schürz:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology. **Péter Braun:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Enrico Antonio Chiaradia:** Writing – review & editing. **Joana Eichenberger:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Mohammad Reza Eini:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation. **Csilla Farkas:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Marie Anne Eurie Forio:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Investigation, Data curation. **Peter Goethals:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Data curation. **Piroska Kassai:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Štěpán Marval:** Writing – review & editing. **Diego G. Panique-Casso:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Lorenzo Sanguanini:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Moritz Shore:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Brigitta Szabó:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Investigation, Data curation. **Petr Slavík:** Writing – review & editing. **Felix Witing:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Software availability:

- Name of software: SWATtunR
- Developers: Svajunas Plunge & Christoph Schürz
- Contact: svajunas.plunge@sggw.edu.pl
- Date first available: April 24, 2024
- Software required: RStudio
- Program language: R
- Source code at: <https://github.com/biopsichas/SWATtunR>
- Documentation: <https://biopsichas.github.io/SWATtunR/>
- Data required for local installation and use of software is available in the GitHub repository.

Funding

This project received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 862756.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

We thank Jim Kiniry (USDA, ARS) and Manyowa (Norman) Meki (Texas A&M Agrilife Research) for their guidance on crop parameterisation.

We thank Jeffrey Arnold (USDA, ARS) for responding to SWAT +

code issues, explaining the tools application, and providing details on its functionality.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2025.106794>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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